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THE ROLE OF UNESCO IN THE AREA OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. International organizations in the world are influencing the social, political, cultural and economic processes taking place today. Therefore, it is important to study their activities in detail. The article examines the impact of international organizations and their networks and these institutions on the field of culture. Also, the history of the organization of UNESCO, a specialized institution of the United Nations Organization for science, education and culture, and its practical work on the study and preservation of cultural monuments are analyzed.

Key words: League of Nations, UN, San Francisco, UNESCO, cultural monuments

The 20th century was marked in the history of humanity as a period of radical change in the fields of socio-economic, political, cultural, science, technology, and communication. Today, in the era of ensuring regional and global security, peace, and strengthening international cooperation, the role, role and participation of international organizations in preserving the high humanitarian ideals of the countries and peoples of the world, uniting them on the basis of national and universal values, is of great importance. .

Humanity has established various organizations and interacted with each other under any historical conditions, and solved the problems based on the principles of cooperation. The role of these organizations in the mutual socio-economic, political and cultural relations of states and peoples has gained importance.

International organizations are associations of states or non-governmental national societies formed to achieve common goals in political, economic, social, scientific and technical, cultural and other fields, and are one of the most important forms of multilateral cooperation between states. According to their activities, international organizations are divided into such types as global, regional, political, economic, international intergovernmental, and international non-governmental organizations.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the number of international organizations was over a thousand, and in the 1990s, 300 of them, and in the early 2000s, 500 of them were non-governmental organizations. According to the London-based political research association, as of 2013, 33 universal, 33 trans-regional, 193 regional, and a total of 261 international organizations are operating in the world.

The political and economic processes that took place at the end of the 19th century and the 20th century caused the role and importance of international organizations to increase. The first international organizations in the world were the International Telegraph Union and the International Geodetic Union in 1865, the World Metrology Organization in 1873, the International Postal Union in 1874, and the International Union for the Publication of Customs Tariffs in 1890. All of them later got the status of UN specialized institutions. However, as the first universal international organization, the League of Nations remained in history.

The League of Nations aimed to coordinate political and economic processes, prevent conflicts between countries, and ensure human rights. The organization was formed in 1919 after the First World War. Although the League of Nations is considered the first international universal organization, it did not have enough experience in international socio-political processes. According to the mandate system and charter, it had many powers, but in practice it could not implement any major event at the international level. This led to the emergence of

fascism and the second world war, which posed a great threat to humanity. This is the reason for his failure and termination of his international career. That is, the League of Nations existed between two world wars.

At the end of the 20th century and into the 21st century, the United Nations Organization is noted as the largest and most influential international organization in the world, with a wide sphere of socio-economic, political and cultural influence. The UN is the only organization of the peoples of the world that is considered the center of solving human problems. Big and small, rich and poor, countries belonging to different social groups, with different political, economic and cultural interests, which are members of the UN, have the right to express their ideas and opinions.

The United Nations Charter was developed at an international conference in San Francisco, USA from April 25 to June 25, 1945 with the participation of representatives of 50 countries, signed on June 26, 1945 and entered into force on October 24. A state that has become a member of the UN accepts the obligations of the UN Charter as a full-fledged subject of international relations.

Since the establishment of the organization, the world's political, social, i also means receiving. When the UN was founded, the number of its members was 51 countries. As of 2015, 193 countries are equal members of the organization.

As stated in the Charter of the UN institution UNESCO, "Ideas of war appear in people's minds, so it is necessary to instill in people's minds the idea of protecting peace." Science, education and culture are important in this regard.

Among the specialized institutions of the United Nations, UNESCO has a great place and importance. The organization is a UN agency on science, education and culture issues. UNESCO was founded on November 16, 1945, and its headquarters is located in Paris, the capital of France. This organization operates in the fields of science, culture, fight against poverty, protection of ecology, sustainable development and intercultural dialogue, education, information and

communication.

During their joint activities, the countries that have become members of UNESCO accept and ratify agreements, fulfill their rights and obligations. Also, the organization announces various awards and prizes together with countries and their governments and bodies. Representatives of member states participate in UNESCO's advisory committees.

UNESCO is committed to promoting peace and security for all peoples, regardless of race, sex, language, or religion, and the United As stated in the Charter of the United Nations, it was created for this very purpose. Organization

- It helps the peoples to come closer and understand each other using all the media.

- Recommends the conclusion of international agreements,

- Stimulates the development of public education and the spread of culture,

- The members of the organization cooperate with the states and expand educational activities at their request,

- In order to ensure the independence and inviolability of the member states in order to preserve the uniqueness of their culture and education system, the organization essentially refuses any interference in the internal competence of these states.

UNESCO was established on November 16, 1945, after the Second World War, and the UNESCO charter came into force on November 4, 1946. The same date is celebrated all over the world as the day of the establishment of UNESCO. After the establishment of the organization, the practical dialogue between UNESCO and the countries has been consistently developing, and partnership relations are becoming stronger. Today, organizations and countries are effectively implementing joint measures in priority directions, and special attention is being paid to intensifying cooperation in the field of preserving the unique cultural and historical heritage of peoples.

In short, preservation of customs, traditions and traditions of mankind that have been going on for thousands of years is an important process for today. Every country with independence feels that it is its objective necessity to focus on the development of science and education, to preserve national customs and traditions and to pass them on to the next generation, and to exchange ideas with the countries of the world and their leading scientists. and the current period requires that they establish cooperation relations in these areas. The organization that coordinates all of the above tasks throughout the world is UNESCO.

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